

Supplementary Table 1: Decorative methods and decorative elements in utility ware and fine ware sherds in the 2016 sample from the Sanders site.

Decorative Method and Decorative Elements	Rim	Body	N
<u>Grog-Tempered</u>			
UTILITY WARES			
<i>Appliqued</i>			
applied nodes	-	2	2
parallel applied ridges	-	1	1
straight applied ridge	-	4	4
<i>Brushed</i>			
parallel brushed	-	1	1
<i>Corn Cob Impressed</i>			
corn cob impressed	1	1	2
<i>Incised</i>			
cross-hatched incised lines	1	1	2
curvilinear incised line	-	3	3
diagonal incised lines	3	-	3
diagonal opposed incised lines	-	3	3
horizontal incised lines	-	1	1
opposed incised lines	-	5	5
parallel incised lines	-	7	7
straight incised line	-	17	17
<i>Incised-Punctated</i>			
tool punctated row below lip and above horizontal incised line	1	-	1
<i>Notched</i>			
lip notched	1	-	1

Pinched

straight pinched ridge	-	1	1
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Punctated

cane punctated row	-	1	1
finger nail punctated rows	1	8	9
linear tool punctated rows	-	3	3
tool punctated row/rows	1	6	7
parallel tool punctated rows	-	2	2
single tool punctate	-	3	3

FINE WARES

Engraved

circular ticked el. and curvilinear cross-hatched zone	-	1	1
circular el. and cross-hatched engraved zone	-	1	1
cross-hatched engraved zone	-	1	1
curvilinear engraved lines that end in hooked arms	-	1	1
curvilinear cross-hatched zones	-	1	1
curvilinear engraved line	-	2	2
diagonal engraved lines	1	2	3
diagonal opposed engraved lines	-	1	1
diagonal cross-hatched zones	1	-	1
diagonal hatched zone	1	-	1
hatched triangle element with diagonal lines	1	-	1
horizontal engraved lines	2	1	3
horizontal engraved line with excised tick marks	1	-	1
horizontal and vertical engraved lines and hatched	1	-	1
pendant triangle el.			
parallel engraved lines	-	1	1
engraved scroll line and cross-hatched engraved scroll	1	-	1
fill zone			
straight engraved line	-	2	2
straight engraved line and cross-hatched engraved	-	1	1
zone			
straight engraved line and diagonal engraved zone	-	1	1
with a hatched line			

Engraved-Red Slipped

diagonal engraved lines and int./ext. red-slipped	2	-	2
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Slipped

exterior red-slipped	-	24	24
interior/exterior red-slipped	-	7	7
Sub-total, grog-tempered	20	117	137

Bone-Tempered

UTILITY WARE

Brushed

horizontal brushed	1	-	1
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Incised

parallel incised lines	-	1	1
straight incised line	-	1	1

Punctated

linear tool punctated rows	-	1	1
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FINE WARE

Engraved

cross-hatched engraved lines	-	1	1
engraved triangle el. and diagonal engraved lines	1	-	1
straight engraved line	-	1	1

Slipped

exterior red-slipped	-	5	5
interior/exterior red-slipped	1	1	2

Slipped-Punctated

fingernail punctated rows on ext. and red-slipped int.	-	1	1
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Sub-total, bone-tempered	3	12	15
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Shell-Tempered

UTILITY WARE

Appliqued

parallel appliqued ridges	-	2	2
straight appliqued ridge	-	1	1

Punctated

tool punctated row	-	1	1
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FINE WARE

Slipped

exterior red-slipped	-	1	1
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Sub-total, shell-tempered	-	5	5
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Total	23	134	157
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Supplementary Table 2: Chipped Stone tools from the Sanders site in the March 2016 sample.

Provenience	Raw Material	Comments
Arrow points		
East Mound	very dark gray chert	blade fragment
West Mound	very dark gray chert	Bonham; W (16.8 mm); Th (3.6 mm); SW (5.2 mm)
Area 5	jasper	blade fragment
ST 27, 0-20 cm (Area 9)	novaculite	blade fragment, Th (2.4 mm)
ST 28, 0-20 cm (Area 9)	light grayish-red chert	blade fragment, Th (2.4 mm)
Area 13	gray chert	triangular point fragment; Th (2.0 mm)
Area 25	light gray chert	triangular with concave base, W (13.7 mm); Th (2.9 mm)
Area 29	dark gray chert	triangular point fragment, Th (3.5 mm)
Area 29	yellowish-brown chert	triangular point fragment with flat base, Th (1.9 mm)
Area 36	black chert	triangular with flat base, L (14.0 mm); W (8.9 mm); Th (2.0 mm)
Area 37	grayish-yellow chert	triangular with concave base; W (16.0 mm); Th (3.4 mm)
Dart points		
Area 5	siltstone	Gary point preform
Area 16	very dark grayish-brown chert	Gary point, L (36.9 mm); W (28.0 mm); Th (7.4 mm); SW (12.1 mm)
Area 17	quartzite	Gary point; L (38.2 mm); W (23.7 mm); Th (6.9 mm); SW (13.9 mm)
Bifaces		
Area 6	quartzite	biface preform fragment
Area 9	gray chert	biface fragment

Scrapers

East Mound	dark gray chert	side scraper
East Mound	very dark gray chert	side scraper (bilateral)
East Mound	dark gray-black chert	end scraper
Area 5	dark gray chert	end-side scraper
Area 5	very dark grayish-brown chert	side scraper
Area 6	brownish-gray chert	side scraper
Area 6	very dark gray chert	end-side scraper (bilateral)
Area 6	brownish-gray chert	end-side scraper
Area 9	black chert	end-side scraper
Area 9	brownish-gray chert	side scraper
Area 9	very dark gray chert	end scraper
ST 24, 20-40 cm (Area 9)	grayish-white chert	end scraper
Area 13	black chert	side scraper
Area 13	reddish-gray chert	side scraper (bilateral)
Area 13	gray chert	side scraper
Area 17	novaculite	end-side scraper (bilateral)
Area 17	black chert	end-side scraper (bilateral)
Area 17	gray chert	side scraper (bilateral)
Area 17	very dark gray chert	end-side scraper
Area 17	gray chert	side scraper
Area 17	dark grayish-brown chert	end scraper
Area 17	gray chert	end scraper
Area 29	grayish-dark brown chert	end-side scraper
Area 34	yellowish-gray chert	end-side scraper (bilateral)
Area 34	gray chert	end-side scraper
Area 36	very dark grayish-brown chert	end-side scraper
Area 37	dark gray chert	side scraper
Area 37	very dark gray chert	side scraper
Area 39	dark gray chert	end-side scraper
Area 39	dark gray chert	side scraper (bilateral)

Perforators and Drills

Area 9	reddish-gray chert	bifacial drill
Area 17	white-yellow chert	bifacial perforator
Area 37	very dark gray chert	perforator; in combination with an area of unilateral use/retouch

Flake Tools

East Mound	light gray chert	unilateral used edge
East Mound	very dark gray chert	bilateral used edges
East Mound	black chert	unilateral used edge
Area 5	jasper	unilateral used edge
Area 5	grayish-brown chert	bilateral used edge
Area 5	novaculite	unilateral used edge
Area 5	dark gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 6	dark gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 6	brownish-gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 6	gray-dark brown chert	unilateral used edge
Area 9	dark gray chert	bilateral used edges
Area 9	black chert	bilateral used edges
Area 13	dark gray chert	graver
Area 17	very dark gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 17	reddish-gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 17	dark gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 25	dark grayish-brown chert	unilateral used edge
Area 29	gray-dark gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 34	dark grayish-brown chert	unilateral used edge
Area 34	brownish-gray chert	unilateral used edge
Area 37	dark grayish-brown chert	unilateral used edge
Area 37	dark gray chert	unilateral used edge
